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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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THE RELEVANCE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN TEACHING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: Artificial Intelligence (AI) is transforming education by introducing innovative tools and methods for teaching and learning. In the context of English language education, AI provides personalized learning experiences, real-time feedback, and increased accessibility. This paper examines the applications of AI in English language teaching, as well as its benefits, challenges, and future implications for both educators and learners.

Key words: Artificial Intelligence, English language, language learning, tools, strategies, teaching, methods.

Annotatsiya: Sun'iy intellekt (SI) ta'lim tizimini o'qitish va o'rganish jarayoniga innovatsion vositalar va metodlarni joriy etish orqali tubdan o'zgartirmoqda. Ingliz tilini o'qitish kontekstida SI shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim imkoniyatlarini, real vaqt rejimida fikr-mulohaza olishni hamda ta'limga kengroq kirish imkoniyatlarini ta'minlaydi. Mazkur maqolada ingliz tilini o'qitishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish yo'nalishlari, uning afzalliklari, mavjud muammolari va kelajakdagi istiqbollari tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, ingliz tili, til o'rganish, vositalar, strategiya, o'qitish, metodlar.

Аннотация: Искусственный интеллект (ИИ) трансформирует систему образования, внедряя инновационные инструменты и методы обучения. В контексте преподавания английского языка ИИ предоставляет персонализированные образовательные возможности, обратную связь в реальном времени и расширяет доступ к обучению. В статье рассматриваются направления применения искусственного интеллекта в обучении английскому языку, его преимущества, существующие проблемы и перспективы развития.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, английский язык, изучение языка, инструменты, стратегия, обучение, методы.

INTRODUCTION

The integration of technology in education has significantly evolved over the past decades. Recently, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a powerful tool in language learning. English, being a global language, requires effective teaching strategies that address diverse learner needs. The rapid advancement of AI is reshaping numerous sectors, including education. In English Language Teaching (ELT), AI is becoming an increasingly powerful tool for facilitating personalized learning, immediate feedback, and interactive practice environments. AI-driven tools are transforming traditional teaching methods by offering adaptive, interactive, and efficient learning environments.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Reading plays a key role in the process of learning English. It not only enhances knowledge but also promotes thinking and social adaptability. Incorporating English storybooks into teaching broadens students' knowledge, improves reading ability and grammatical comprehension, and cultivates interest in learning English (An, 2021). The application of information technology tools enhances the modernization of education, creates a rich learning environment, and strengthens students' motivation and engagement (Zhang, 2022). Therefore, educational institutions should emphasize reading and utilize technological tools to provide better learning resources (Krijgsman, 2018).

Technological innovations have significantly influenced English language teaching. Traditional methods are increasingly supplemented by digital technologies that enable more effective language practice. AI tools such as chatbots, intelligent learning platforms, and automated writing assistants create new opportunities

for interactive and individualized learning. Research shows that AI systems can provide personalized tasks, feedback, and recommendations (Luckin et al., 2016). Additionally, AI enhances speaking, reading, and writing skills through technologies such as speech recognition and natural language processing. These tools provide immediate feedback and support independent learning. AI also increases student motivation and engagement by creating dynamic learning environments (Chen, Chen, & Lin, 2020).

However, challenges remain, including limited digital literacy among teachers and students and the need to use AI as a supportive rather than a replacement tool in education.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is based on a qualitative analytical approach focusing on the integration of AI tools in English language teaching. Various AI applications and platforms are analyzed to understand their role in enhancing language learning. The research examines AI-supported tools such as intelligent tutoring systems, chatbots, speech recognition technologies, and automated assessment tools.

The methodology also involves reviewing existing literature and practical examples of AI implementation in classrooms, including tools like Mentimeter, Gencraft, and AI-based grading systems. The study evaluates how these tools contribute to personalized learning, interactive engagement, and administrative efficiency.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis shows that AI technologies provide several advantages in English language teaching. One of the most important benefits is personalized learning, where AI systems adapt content based on learners' performance and needs. AI tools also improve speaking, reading, and writing skills by offering immediate feedback on pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary.

Interactive platforms, virtual assistants, and chatbots create engaging environments that encourage students to practice more frequently. AI tools also assist teachers by helping them design creative teaching materials, generate tasks, and manage classroom activities more efficiently. Additionally, AI reduces administrative workload by analyzing student data, tracking progress, and identifying learning gaps.

Despite these benefits, some limitations are identified. AI tools may lack personalized feedback in certain contexts, and over-reliance on technology may reduce teacher involvement. Technical challenges and insufficient digital literacy also affect the effective implementation of AI in education.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, Artificial Intelligence has become an essential component of modern English language education. It provides valuable support by offering personalized learning experiences, enhancing student engagement, and improving language skills. AI also assists teachers in designing materials and managing administrative tasks more effectively.

However, AI should not replace teachers but should be used as a supportive tool. Educators must guide students in using AI responsibly and effectively. It is recommended to:

- develop digital literacy skills among teachers and students;
- integrate AI tools with traditional teaching methods;
- use AI for personalized and interactive learning;
- ensure ethical and balanced implementation of AI technologies.

The collaboration between AI and human educators can significantly improve the quality of education when applied appropriately.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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